

Extraction Photometric Studies and Simultaneous Determination of Cobalt and Nickel with 1-Phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl Thiocarbamide

S. Q. R. ILYAS and A. P. JOSHI*

Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur 440 010

Manuscript received 1 July 1978, revised 19 September 1980, accepted 29 January 1981

A thio compound, 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide, is used for the extraction spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and nickel. The complexes get extracted in chloroform and are stable. The orange coloured Co-PTT complex shows λ_{max} at 400 nm while for the yellowish red Ni-PTT complex, it is 460 nm. Beer's law is followed in the range of 0.13 to 1.33 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of cobalt and 0.66 to 3.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of nickel. The effect of the presence of various diverse ions is studied. It is possible to determine cobalt and nickel by simultaneous spectrophotometry. The method is simple, sensitive and applicable to trace quantities.

A number of organic reagents containing thio or other functional groups have been suggested for photometric determination of cobalt and nickel¹. Grtler² and Mathur³ have recently suggested methods for the trace determination of these two metals. A new method based on the reaction of cobalt with a derivative of diacetylmonoxime has been recommended⁴. It, however, requires three hours at 90° for full colour development. The use of thiodibenzoyl methane⁵ and thiobenzoyl acetone⁶ has been made for simultaneous determination of nickel and cobalt with some advantage. In the present work, a new thio compound 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide (PTT) has been used for the extraction spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and nickel. The method proposed is simple and also makes possible to determine two metal ions simultaneously. Extraction studies of platinum with PTT have been reported from laboratory⁷.

Experimental

PTT was prepared in the laboratory and purified.

The standard Co(II) and Ni(II) solutions were prepared by dissolving their AR grade sulphates in distilled water and acidified suitably. The working solutions prepared were, Co=10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and Ni=20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

A sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH 5.0 was used in the studies. It was prepared by mixing the solutions (2M) in required ratio.

Absorbance measurements were made on a Beckman model DU-2 spectrophotometer.

General procedure: To a suitable aliquot of metal ion solution (2-20 μg of Co, 10-55 μg of Ni) add 5 ml of PTT solution of required concentration. ($1.35 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $2.04 \times 10^{-3} M$ for Co and Ni respectively). Make the pH to 5.0 by addition of 5 ml of acetate buffer. Maintaining total volume to 25 ml, allow the mixtures to stand for 45 minutes for full colour development. Transfer the orange-red coloured solutions to a separating funnel and equilibrate with 10 ml of chloroform for 30 seconds. Separate the organic layer, make up the volume to 15 ml and measure the absorbance at 400 and 460 nm for cobalt and nickel respectively against reagent blank. Estimate the quantity of cobalt and nickel in an unknown solution from the calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Extraction behaviour: The extraction behaviour of Co-PTT and Ni-PTT complexes as a function of pH was studied by varying pH of the aqueous phase to different values. Extraction increases from pH 3.5 to 4.5 and is quantitative in the range 5.0-6.0. The use of succinic acid-borax and universal buffer is equally satisfactory to that of acetate buffer to maintain pH=5.0 of the aqueous phase. The extraction is poor when other acids and buffers are used. The stability of the complexes is very high as is evident from the absorbance remaining constant for 36 hours. Chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, toluene and ethyl acetate quantitatively extract the metal ion. In *n*-butanol and hexanol, it is found to be 90% and 56% respectively. The values of sensitivity (Sandell's) and molar absorptivity ($\text{litre mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) for Co-PTT system, are 0.00176 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$ and 3.3×10^4 respectively and for Ni-

PTT system, these values are $0.00437 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and 1.34×10^4 respectively.

The Beer's law range and the optimum range for accurate determination as determined by Ringbom plot are 0.13-1.33 and 0.42-1.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ for cobalt and 0.66-3.66 and 1.0-3.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ for nickel.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of the presence of various ions was studied and the tolerance limit is given in Table 1. The limit was found to be almost same for both Ni and Co systems. For some interfering ions, masking agents were used and limit was determined. The ions edta , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Ir^{3+} and Pt^{4+} interfere strongly in both cobalt and nickel systems.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Co = 10 μg , pH=5.0, λ_{max} =400 nm
Ni = 20 μg , pH=5.0, λ_{max} =460 nm

Tolerance limit (μg)	Ion present
5.0×10^3	Br^- , I^- , SCN^- , NO_3^- , CO_3^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} , malonate, succinate, tartrate, K^+ , VO_2^+ , Tl^+ , As^{3+}
1.0×10^3	NO_2^- , oxalate, citrate, $\text{Ag}^+(\text{a})$, Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Y^{3+} , $\text{Th}^{4+}(\text{c})$
5.0×10^2	$\text{Mn}^{3+}(\text{b})$, Zn^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , $\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{b})$, Ga^{3+} , Ce^{4+} , W^{6+}
2.0×10^2	Ru^{3+} , Rh^{3+} , In^{3+} , La^{3+} , Os^{6+}
Masked with a) thiourea, b) ascorbic acid and c) sulfosalicylic acid.	

Simultaneous determination of nickel and cobalt :

The absorption maxima of nickel and cobalt are widely separated. The use of this was made in determining the two metal ions in a mixture. Absorbances were measured at 400 nm and 460 nm and suitable spectrophotometric equations were applied. Two conditions for use of these equations were satisfied, viz., the absorbances of the complexes were additive at the wavelengths studied and Beer's law was obeyed by the complexes at both the wavelengths. Molar absorptivities of the systems at both the λ_{max} were determined.

These values ($\epsilon_{\text{Co}} = 3.3 \times 10^4$ at 400 nm and 1.47×10^4 at 460 nm ; $\epsilon_{\text{Ni}} = 6.52 \times 10^3$ at 400 nm and 1.34×10^4 at 460 nm) are useful in further calculations. Mixtures of cobalt and nickel in appropriate proportions were made and analysed. The results obtained for the different systems are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF COBALT AND NICKEL

Taken μg Co+Ni	Found μg Co+Ni	Error %	
		Co	Ni
10+40	9.85+40.7	1.5	1.7
20+30	19.78+30.29	1.0	0.8
30+20	29.75+20.05	0.8	0.2
15+50	14.95+50.72	0.3	1.4
25+35	25.22+34.92	0.9	0.2

Precision and accuracy : The methods suggested for cobalt and nickel are simple and applicable at trace concentrations. The reagent is also sufficiently sensitive and the results are reproducible. The relative mean deviation observed was for cobalt system 0.66% and for nickel system 1.28%. The average recovery of a metal is $99.9 \pm 1\%$. The simultaneous determination of cobalt and nickel gives somewhat poorer accuracy.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head, Chemistry Department, Nagpur University for encouragement.

References

1. A. K. DE, S. M. KHOPKAR and R. A. CHALMERS, Solvent Extraction of Metals, Van Nostrand, Reinhold, London, 1970.
2. O. GÜRTLER, Z. Anal. Chem., 1977, 284, 206.
3. S. P. MATHUR, J. Inst. Chem., 1976, 48, 300.
4. R. M. PEARSON and H. J. SEIM, Anal. Chem., 1977, 49, 580.
5. E. UHLEMANN and B. SCHUKNECHT, Anal. Chem. Acta, 1973, 63, 236.
6. M. V. R. MURTHI and S. M. KHOPKAR, Talanta, 1976, 23, 246.
7. R. M. UTTARWAR and A.P. JOSHI, Z. Anal. Chem., 1977, 287, 317.